

**Challenges and solutions for more effective
programming and implementation
of the multi-actor approach (MAA)
Focus Group process May–June 2024**

COORDINATION OF THE PROCESS AND COMPILATION OF THE REPORT

Kaie Laaneväli-Vinokurov

Jordi Pietx

WITH CONTRIBUTIONS FROM

Participants to the Focus Group process

PREMIERE

PREPARING MULTI-ACTOR PROJECTS IN A CO-CREATIVE WAY

GA no. 101086531

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This final report compiles all the challenges and solutions identified towards a more effective programming and implementation of the multi-actor approach. The contents of this report are the result of the different discussions and reflections of this first PREMIERE focus group, between May 3rd and June 12th, 2024. The challenges and solutions are presented in 5 thematic blocks, with a prioritisation developed at the last remote discussion meeting. Some of the contents have been slightly edited for coherence, and all the ideas proposed during the process are reflected in.

This process was organised by the PREMIERE project and hosted by the European Commission.

Disclaimer: The responsibility for the information and views set out in this background document lies entirely with the authors and cannot in any circumstances be regarded as the official position of the European Commission or its services.

OVERVIEW OF THE REPORT

This report, prepared by the PREMIERE project, is based on the results of the Focus Group “Challenges and solutions for more effective programming and implementation of the multi-actor approach (MAA)” that was conducted between May 3rd and June 12th, 2024, and hosted by the European Commission.

The report compiles the challenges and solutions identified to enhance the programming and implementation of the Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) within Horizon Europe projects. The focus group process involved extensive discussions and reflections by key stakeholders from five groups: policy officers¹, project officers², NCPs³, external experts⁴, and project coordinators along with other informed and interested stakeholders and experts.

The report consists of seven sections. **The Introduction and Process of the Focus Group** section outlines the background and objectives of the focus group and details the steps of the focus group process, including the initial kick-off workshop, the phases of online interactive discussions, and the final joint session.

The Structure of the Reported Challenges and Solutions section explains how the challenges and solutions are organized within the report. It provides a table with the number of challenges and related solutions, categorized by their timeframe for implementation (short-term, medium-term, and long-term).

¹ Directorate-General policy officers: DG AGRI, DG Environment, DG Grow and DG RTD (DG Research and Innovation)

² Research Executive Agency (REA) and PRIMA Mediterranean Programme

³ National Contact Points for Horizon Cluster 6

⁴ with experience in multi-actor project proposal evaluation.

The core of the report, **Challenges and Solutions Identified**, presents the challenges and solutions identified during the focus group discussions. The challenges are organized into five thematic blocks. Each block includes a detailed list of challenges and their corresponding solutions, along with a suggested timeframe for application.

The Recommendations on the Multi-Actor Approach Definition section compiles suggestions for improving the official definition of the MAA and other work programme content.

The References section lists the documents generated during the focus group process and other relevant materials that informed the discussions and the report's content.

The two Annexes provide the number of participants who contributed to the focus group, categorized by actor groups, and the list of challenges identified during the focus group process that were not included in the final compilation.

1 INTRODUCTION AND PROCESS OF THE FOCUS GROUP

The PREMIERE project focus group, hosted by the European Commission, facilitated a co-creative online discussion to address **challenges, solutions and recommendations for more effective programming and implementation of the multi-actor approach (MAA)** within Horizon Europe projects (Cluster 6, Horizon Missions, Partnerships and other).

The objective of the focus group was to identify limitations and bottlenecks in the programming and administration of MAA project Call Topics and to collaboratively develop solutions.

The focus group process was organized into four iterative steps illustrated in the Figure 1, and briefly summarized below. Section 5 below includes the references and links to the main results of each step.

Figure 1: Overview of the Focus Group process

1. A 'kick-off' online workshop on May 3rd, introduced the MAA concept and outlined the steps of the focus group process. The workshop was

recorded to ensure that participants who joined later had the opportunity to be informed on the same level as all other participants. Participants were presented with a background paper to set the base for the initial discussion.

2. The first phase of the online interactive focus group discussion from May 3rd to May 17th where participants identified challenges related to the MAA in five specific key actor groups:

- 1) Policy officers (Directorate-General policy officers: DG AGRI, DG Environment, and DG Research and Innovation),
- 2) Project officers (Research Executive Agency (REA),
- 3) NCPs (National Contact Points for Horizon Cluster 6),
- 4) External experts (With experience in multi-actor project proposal evaluation),
- 5) Project coordinators, and other informed/interested stakeholders/experts.

After the first session, a synthesis of challenges was created, summarizing the identified challenges from the five actor groups. Discussions of the first phase remained available for reference in reading-only mode during the whole focus group process. The synthesis of challenges was shared with focus group participants and provided context for moving into the second phase of the discussions about co-creating solutions and recommendations.

3. The second phase of the online interactive focus group discussion from May 29th to June 6th where all the participants collaboratively co-created solutions and recommendations. In the second phase, identified challenges were divided into five challenge blocks:

- 1) Challenge Block #1: Communicating basic information and terminology related to MAA.
- 2) Challenge Block #2: Programming and evaluation of the MAA calls.
- 3) Challenge Block#3: Creating an enabling environment to support applicants and beneficiaries.
- 4) Challenge Block #4: Developing proposals for MAA calls.
- 5) Challenge Block #5: Implementing MAA projects in practice.

During the second phase, participants had the opportunity to propose additional challenges they found missing, with the primary focus being on finding solutions and proposing recommendations for the identified challenges. Participants were continuously encouraged to revise their input, engage with others, and reply to each other's comments throughout the focus group process.

4. **The final online joint session on June 12th**, where participants reviewed and validated the identified challenges and collaboratively improved the proposed solutions. This session was structured into breakout groups focusing on different challenge blocks. The first part of the session focused on consolidating and validating the identified challenges, discussing their relevance, and prioritizing them. The second part of the session focused on collaboratively improving solutions and developing a set of solutions for each challenge.

2 STRUCTURE OF THE REPORTED CHALLENGES & SOLUTIONS

The following section 3 presents the challenges and solutions identified during the focus group process and organised in five blocks (Table 1). The table format is intended to facilitate a practical review and selection of potential solutions by the EC units involved. The tables also include a suggested time frame for the application of the solutions: Short-term (2025 Horizon Europe Work Plans), Medium-term (2026-2027 Horizon Europe Work Plans), Long-term (EC Framework Program FP10, 2028-3034).

Finally, a separate Section 4 compiles a list of suggestions on the MAA definition and the contents of the Work Programmes related to this MAA. These suggestions emerged during all the focus group process and are listed exactly as proposed by participants, without any editing or group review, meaning that some may overlap or repeat the same idea.

The five blocks of challenges and solutions were identified during the focus group process and follow the same classification in this report. The challenges included are also a result of the process and in the report have sometimes been re-written resulting from the final session discussions, while a majority follow the same text proposed before the final session. Some challenges may overlap in different blocks, as the blocks are clearly not closed boxes.

The solutions have undergone final editing for the preparation of this report, to adjust to the discussions of the final session, as well as to the expert consideration of PREMIERE team. This means they have been re-written or merged between several of them.

Block#1 on Basic information and terminology was excluded from the final session that focused on the other four blocks, therefore, prioritising in the block#1 is solely based on criteria by the PREMIERE team.

The challenges and solutions shown on the table with white background were prioritized as most relevant by the participants at the final focus group session, while those in the grey background did not receive a priority selection. Annex 2 presents a small number of challenges identified during the focus group process that were considered to be excluded from this final report. The reasons for each exclusion are also explained in the annex.

Where an asterisk* appears in the text of a solution it is an indication that the references section 5 of this report provides further details on that matter.

Finally, note that the solutions are presented always in parallel to a certain challenge, however some solutions may also contribute to more than one challenge, and this is not indicated in the document. Also, solutions have not been filtered for duplicity or overlap, thus clearly some of them respond to a ‘one or another’ choice.

Table 1: Number of identified challenges and solutions on programming and implementation of the multi-actor approach

Challenge Block	No. of Challenges	No. of related solutions	Solutions		
			Short term	Medium term*	Long term*
Block #1: Communicating basic information and terminology related to MAA	10	15	4	9	2
Block #2: Programming and evaluation of the MAA calls	11	23	10	6	7
Block#3: Creating an enabling environment to	5	18	4	6	8

support applicants and beneficiaries					
Block#4: Developing proposals for MAA calls	8	18	6	7	5
Block #5: Implementing MAA projects in practice	16	22	10	5	7

**Solutions rated as short-medium are accounted for as Medium term. Those medium-long are accounted for as Long.*

3 CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS IDENTIFIED⁵

3.1 Challenge Block #1: Communicating basic information and terminology related to MAA

Ch. no.	Final synthesis challenges	So. no.	Final synthesis solutions	Solution Timeframe
1.1	The MAA concept itself and others related (AKIS, beneficiaries, actors, end-users, stakeholders, etc.) are often unclear at national level. Clear and translated definitions, with the instructions of the kind of actors to be included, are needed for all involved	1.1.1	When a new MAA proposal is registered by a coordinator, the F&T portal should send an automated message with a clear explanation on what it means to comply with MAA, including a glossary of key concepts and links to Q&A, relevant resources and training materials.	Short - Medium
		1.1.2	Have official translations of key MAA terms into all EU languages to ensure clarity for all actors, particularly the term 'multi-actor approach' itself.	Medium
1.2	Info days and brokerage events are fundamental for better promotion and a common understanding of the MAA, but they need to better share resources and practical approaches and reach a broader audience, including end-users who may not typically attend such events.	1.2.1	Increase the number of national/regional info days and other events (in native language) targeting specific stakeholders. In these, explain the MAA concept, clarify how end-users should be involved in proposal drafting and offer clear and acceptable incentives for their participation.	Short
		1.2.2	Design and use activities beyond info days to target specific actors, formats like working groups, focus groups, brokerage events, and practical cases of project presentations may be more effective for engagement. Additionally, there should be follow-up events and discussions to address ongoing concerns.	Medium
		1.2.3	Use the Rubric on the MAA* of PREMIERE, and a selection (positive/negative) former ESR statements presentations and events.	Short

⁵ The challenges and solutions in white background were prioritized as most relevant by the participants at the final focus group session, while those in grey background did not receive a priority selection.

3.1 Challenge Block #1: Communicating basic information and terminology related to MAA

Ch. no.	Final synthesis challenges	So. no.	Final synthesis solutions	Solution Timeframe
1.3	More detailed and practical trainings and resources are needed to help applicants better understand MAA and implement the requirements effectively. Materials from the EC, CARE4BIO, LIAISON, PREMIERE e.g., annotated proposal templates, webinars, and training sessions, are available but need broader communication and use.	1.3.1	Any kind of additional information material (e.g. videos, factsheets, etc.) is welcomed.	Short - Medium
		1.3.2	Provide a compilation or database good practices of well-established MAA for inspiration. The examples must correspond to the diversity of destinations and areas that apply to the MAA.	Short
1.4	There is a need to clearly distinguish between MAA in relation to consortium members and external stakeholders. Only partners can significantly impact project outcomes, and relying solely on stakeholders can undermine the project's effectiveness.	1.4.1	Use the MAA definition to express this clear distinction. A proposal is included in the listing of Definition and Work Programme changes, included as an annex of the FG.	Short - Medium
1.5	The EU Funding & Tenders Portal and the Multi-actor projects page of the CAP Network are valuable online communication channels that are currently underutilized. Optimizing the use of these platforms can enhance the promotion and explanation of MAA, making it more accessible and understandable for all stakeholders.	1.5.1	Increase the promotion of the CAP Network page as a 'one-stop shop' for MAA resources, with cross-references to the Funding & Tenders Portal. Ensure the platforms are highly visible, cross-referenced, and frequently updated. Ensure precise, clear and complete basic information on the MAA in the F&T Portal.	Short - Medium
1.6	Experienced project coordinators, who are often overconfident in their knowledge and skills, may not engage with available MAA resources and strategies. These 'hard-to-reach' coordinators require targeted efforts to ensure they understand and adopt new MAA strategies effectively	1.6.1	Provide specific training to both evaluators and coordinators to improve understanding and implementation of MAA in the proposal.	Long
1.7	Communicating with stakeholders is challenging due to a lack of time and financial resources. One-on-one communication and translations in multi-lingual projects are resource-heavy, especially in agriculture and forestry where many stakeholders do not speak English.	1.7.1	Facilitate and update a toolbox for language management in MAA projects with a selection of the best translation tools for different type of language-based activities and materials, including automated and human-assisted methods, and referencing cost estimates.	Long
1.8	Despite a clear definition of MAA, the differentiation between a stakeholder and an actor in projects remains unclear even after 10 years of its introduction into EU framework programs.	1.8.1	Proposals should clearly explain and justify the MAA and consortium composition, with evaluators assessing their quality based on the project objectives. To ensure this, evaluators must first understand the MAA.	Short

3.1 Challenge Block #1: Communicating basic information and terminology related to MAA

Ch. no.	Final synthesis challenges	So. no.	Final synthesis solutions	Solution Timeframe
		1.8.2	Establish clear definitions that are easily understood by non-English speakers to prevent confusion for coordinators and reviewers.	Medium
1.9	MAA to be better acknowledged as part of existing co-design and co-creation processes, rather than as a completely new concept to avoid confusion amongst applicants.	1.9.1		Medium
1.10	MAA material on agriculture only could be misleading: in Horizon Europe, MAA is applied to many areas beyond agriculture, so when presenting best practices or successful projects, it would be good to cover the variety of areas under CL6. There is a large variety of end-users, not only farmers and foresters, as presented in the definition, so it is important to reflect this variety when producing communication material on MAA.	1.10.1	See 1.2 solutions	Medium

3.2 Challenge Block #2: Programming and evaluation of the MAA calls

Ch. No.	Challenge		Proposed solutions	Solution Timeframe
2.1	<p>Evaluating the MAA objectively as an eligibility criterion is difficult due to varying vocabulary and interpretations across different backgrounds and regions. While a convincing MAA should influence the final project score, the current evaluation process lacks consistency and emphasis on the MAA, leading to subjective assessments.</p>	2.1.1	Coupled solution: 1) Standardise a short paragraph structure in all MAA topic texts explaining why a proposal includes the MAA and what is expected in terms of actors and the expected involvement. 2) Require in the topic text that proposals must include an abstract text making the MAA explicit and indicating how it is addressed in the proposal.	Short
		2.2.2	Define guidelines to ensure clear differentiation and connection of MAA actors (beneficiaries) and external stakeholders involved	Medium
		2.2.3	Incorporate MAA into the technical requirement instead the eligibility criterion to make MAA a concrete aspect of the project's interdisciplinarity and methodology, making it easier for evaluators to assess.	Long
2.2	<p>It is difficult to demonstrate and assess "genuine and sufficient involvement of actors (...) from participation in the development of the project idea" (i.e. actors' involvement in proposals' preparation) during the evaluation. Evaluators need clear criteria to assess the roles and contributions of different partners within the consortium, ensuring alignment with the project's concept and call requirements.</p>	2.2.1	Add specific criteria to the evaluators' grid to assess the distribution of the budget between different partner types to ensure that the financial commitment to diverse actors is explicitly considered during evaluation. In parallel proposal writers need to be informed that their budget distribution will also be evaluated in terms of involvement and commitment of different stakeholders.	Short
		2.2.2	In connection to solution 2.1.1 above, include a special paragraph in the proposal template where applicants must explain the MAA and justify the involvement of each stakeholder in the context of the project's concept and the call's requirements. This paragraph should detail how stakeholders were involved in preparatory meetings, the development of proposal sections, and other relevant activities.	Medium
		2.2.3	Require the proposals coordinators to provide a list of the types of actors involved, along with a justification for their involvement. Allow for flexibility in actor involvement allowing to simply outline the types of actors involved and their roles over the project's duration.	Short
		2.2.4	Evaluation should be more learning-oriented than focused only on deliverables but also on management processes and approaches to change and fostering brokerage with other projects.	Short

3.2 Challenge Block #2: Programming and evaluation of the MAA calls

Ch. No.	Challenge		Proposed solutions	Solution Timeframe
2.3	There is a lack of transparency and understanding regarding the criteria for selecting MAA for specific topics in programming and it is unclear how MAA is evaluated in these contexts (some topics explicitly require collaborations between various sectors but do not explicitly mandate MAA in the body of the topic text).	2.3.1	Establish an editorial board for the call topic drafting process that provides a systematic review after the initial drafting, involving different units to ensure clarity, consistency, and alignment with MAA requirements. The board will verify whether the inclusion of MAA is justified and consistent across similar topics. The board can recommend redrafting.	Long
		2.3.2	Create a figure of "Coordinator / Advisor on the MAA" for the topic drafting units, to supervise the process of MAA labelling of work programme topics.	Medium
2.4	MAA is assessed differently depending on the topic: core part of the topic (e.g. AKIS): significant weakness; technological topic: minor shortcoming; it is hard to understand the importance of MAA in a given topic, lighter stakeholder engagement could be considered in some cases	2.4.1	This is reasonable and it is also associated to the differences that MAA can have when applied to different sectors, e.g. farmers involvement in Agri project has different characteristics to brand owners in a biobased one. Therefore, a different degree and type of MAA in different topics makes sense, and this should be clear in the topic text.	Short
2.5	MAA topics with a technology (product, service, etc.) component do not always result in ready to use (TRL up to 8) solutions at the end of the project, while the definition and requirements clearly indicate that this should be the primary objective (i.e. optimization is sought). At the same time, MAA is particularly useful for 'wicked' problems⁶, where there is no consensus nor clear solutions identified among actors, and have to evolve in a transformational context, where TRL does not apply.	2.5.1	Requirements for the MAA should clarify on this. If the goal is a market technological solution, also, call texts should indicate it. For transformative goals, other requirement should be developed instead of TRL, such as the evolution of strategies and activities for societal change, changes in networks, or increased empowerment for change.	Long
2.6	Extensive and complex requirements in MAA calls can lead to proposals that focus on ticking boxes rather than detailing concrete actions, complicating the evaluation process.	2.6.1	Include a dedicated section in the proposal template where applicants must describe how the network has established a MAA during proposal preparation and how it plans to leverage this approach throughout the project.	Long
		2.6.2	Detail how the budget distribution reflects the involvement and commitment of different stakeholders.	Medium

⁶ A wicked problem is a problem, usually social or cultural, that is challenging or impossible to solve either because not enough is understood about the problem, the number of stakeholders involved, the number of varying opinions, the economic burden, or the impact of these problems with other problems. (Source: <https://wicked-problem.press.plymouth.edu/chapter/what-is-a-wicked-problem/> visited 8.7.24).

3.2 Challenge Block #2: Programming and evaluation of the MAA calls

Ch. No.	Challenge		Proposed solutions	Solution Timeframe
		2.6.3	Adopt a strategy for the use of MAA in different areas: in some cases, MAA is too heavy, co-design & co-creation can be done without the 7 requirements, “not about us without us” as co-creation motto	Long
		2.6.4	Separate the requirements in MAA calls into two distinct lists: one for creating a multi-actor consortium and another for involving multi-actor stakeholders outside the consortium (Definition annex)	Long
2.7	It is difficult programming the MAA in specific sectors (e.g. fisheries and aquaculture) that lack a framework like the EIP AGRI, operational groups, and practice abstracts. Finding effective dissemination solutions at the EU level is not straightforward.	2.7.1	Promote the use of National Rural Networks and EMFAF-funded LAGs that focus on fisheries and aquaculture and other national or regional fish-related projects to include local actors in proposals.	Medium
		2.7.2	Design smaller, more focused call topics specifically for niche sectors like fisheries and aquaculture to ensure competition among potential applicants, making the call topics more accessible and manageable for smaller consortia. This is a strategic decision to be considered.	Medium
2.8	Application templates do not provide precise instructions on crucial aspects related to the MAA.	2.8.1	Develop and integrate an annotated checklist for applying MAA into existing templates like those provided by Care4Bio*.	Short
2.9	It is challenging to fit MAA into the lump-sum scheme and third-party financing (cascading calls) to facilitate the involvement of diverse actors. Lump sum often complicates the involvement of “small” partners, which can lead to artificial segmentation of projects, undermining the multi-actor logic and relevance.	2.9.1	Organize a webinar on how to fit MAA into the lump-sum scheme and third-party financing.	Short
		2.9.2	Annotated templates developed by CARE4BIO: Completing the lump sum section with more details about MAA.	Short
2.10	There is no option for applicants to provide a rebuttal to reviewer comments.	2.10.1	Implement a system where applicants can provide feedback on the reviewers' work through those who review the ESRs before publication to ensure that applicants' concerns are heard and addressed without compromising the efficiency of the evaluation process.	Long
		2.10.2	Ensure adequate review of all 'Complaints about proposal rejection' petitions (see H.Europe Online manual 3.2.6), and use them to improve future review processes.	Short

3.2 Challenge Block #2: Programming and evaluation of the MAA calls

Ch. No.	Challenge		Proposed solutions	Solution Timeframe
2.11	Lack of sufficient time from topic publication to submission	2.11.1	Ensuring adequate time from publication to submission deadlines is necessary to facilitate meaningful MA involvement in proposals and consortia. For instance, government representatives may require several weeks to obtain internal acceptance to participate in the proposal.	Short

3.3 Challenge Block #3: Creating an enabling environment to support applicants and beneficiaries

Ch. No.	Final synthesis challenges		Final synthesis solutions	Solution Timeframe
3.1	Reaching ‘multi-actors’ through different activities remains challenging.	3.1.1	Address the fragmentation of existing enabling environment (very strongly argued by the NCP participants) -> consolidate all existing support materials (including from support projects - PREMIERE, Care4Bio, etc.) for beneficiaries, NCPs etc. and place on a single repository with linkage to it from all relevant places	Medium - Long
		3.1.2	Establish funding programs at the level of RDP or ESF funding that include budget for cross-border networking, events, and conferences involving industry or value chain clusters across regions to enable private players be part of the seed bed for new project idea and proposal consortia. Creative funding models are needed to support a privately driven enabling environment.	Long
		3.1.3	Increase the visibility and accessibility of existing and new supporting materials and tools for MAA applicants (develop a online repository)	Short
		3.1.4	Develop an online repository where actors can register and showcase their interests which allows to filter actors per topic, type, region etc.	Medium
		3.1.5	Organize regular webinars and online meetings to discuss best practices, share updates, and foster collaboration.	Medium - Long
3.2	Seed-funding opportunities for preparing multi-actor proposals are already provided by some national and regional administrations. Are they useful? Could they be further promoted/scaled up? How?	3.2.1	Scale up seed-funding programs provided by national and regional administrations to include more actors, such as NGOs, not just universities. The seed-funding should be structured to offer smaller budgets for participant partners and larger budgets for coordinators.	Medium
		3.2.2	Consider support from the European Commission to finance national seed-funding programs, potentially through a technical assistance payment for Research Ministries.	Long
		3.2.3	Showcase successful seed-funding models (PREMIERE will provide a report), share best practices to help other countries develop or improve their seed-funding schemes and simplify the application requirements for seed-funding by requiring a simple motivation letter and a budget outline.	Short

3.3 Challenge Block #3: Creating an enabling environment to support applicants and beneficiaries

Ch. No.	Final synthesis challenges		Final synthesis solutions	Solution Timeframe
		3.2.4	Reach and resource the smaller partners to engage with consortia. Eligibility criteria to ensure reach those who have most need	Medium
3.3	There is a need for improved networking between acting agencies at the regional (where applicable), national and EU levels.	3.3.1	Showcase successful examples of networking and collaboration practices, such as the "Network to Innovate" run by Baltic countries, Finland, Sweden, and Poland and Bioeconomy initiatives (Bioeast.eu). Foster strong collaborations with relevant organizations at the national and regional levels, as exemplified by successful partnerships like those between Romanian authorities and NCPs, to enhance opportunities and reach end-users effectively.	Medium - Long
		3.3.2	Encourage NCPs and other agencies to join the National Community of Practice of the modernAKIS project to share information and collaborate with relevant organizations.	Short
3.4	Limited human resources make it challenging to provide continuous and comprehensive support to all MAA applicants and beneficiaries. For example, in some countries, there is only one full-time NCP for Cluster 6.	3.4.1	Better dissemination of guides and good practices etc. to NCPs - topic specific etc. tailored for NCPs	Short
		3.4.2	Better co-ordination at MS level between Ministries responsible for NCPs and those familiar with Cluster 6 / MAA	Long
		3.4.3	Transnational support via EU NCP network and national Cluster 6 community	Medium
		3.4.4	Provide specialized training for NCPs on how to effectively utilize tools and materials Identify common needs and actions across different countries to tailor the training accordingly. Organize workshops and training sessions for NCPs to enhance their ability to support applicants. Collaborate with experienced organizations to share best practices and strategies.	Medium - Long
		3.4.5	Introduce a buddy system where experienced coordinating teams of Horizon projects mentor new proposal developers.	Medium
3.5	While programs like CARE4BIO and WIDERA.NET offer travel grants for NCPs and beneficiaries to participate in trainings and brokerage events, the lack of information, distance, and motivation to participate remain significant barriers.	3.5.1	Provide travel grants for actors to participate in various trainings and brokerage events. Establish a working group where several administrative units from different areas meet and exchange knowledge on a regular basis, allowing both sides to learn from each other on an equal level. Invite EU-level representatives to attend regularly.	Long

3.3 Challenge Block #3: Creating an enabling environment to support applicants and beneficiaries

Ch. No.	Final synthesis challenges		Final synthesis solutions	Solution Timeframe
		3.5.2	Survey Cluster 6 NCPs to identify barriers more precisely to enable more targeted solutions. There are multiple barriers to participation which need to be differentiated.	Medium

3.4 Challenge Block #4: Developing proposals for MAA calls

Ch. No.	Final synthesis challenges		Final synthesis solutions	Solution Timeframe
4.1	Writing MAA proposals requires more work and time compared to those involving only researchers.	4.1.1	Ensure accessibility to short videos and infographics with key statements, punchlines, show how to be more effective in proposal preparation.	Medium
		4.1.2	Provide partial reimbursement for project writing to enable more time and effort in developing better-quality proposals (Interreg Europe does this with its funded proposals).	Long
		4.1.3	Monitor the proposal development and ensure that expectations are met and - goals are not lost. (<i>PREMIERE experimented a monthly coaching follow-up of proposal preparation during all its concretion process, with a methodology available</i>)	Short
4.2	Academic and non-academic partners (SMEs, producer organisations, value chain B2B etc): Have different interests & motivation; Are difficult to find and to involve	4.2.1	Develop and disseminate practical examples of how MAA can be included in project design. These examples should highlight successful implementations and common pitfalls to avoid, helping consortia understand what works in MAA and what doesn't.	Medium
		4.2.2	Implement a more extensive EC-supported scoping and network/consortium building phase. This phase should focus on facilitating the formation of diverse consortia, allowing for better alignment of research goals with practical challenges.	Long
		4.2.3	Address the gap between the scientific interests of researchers and the practical challenges faced by other actors, such as farmers. Have key actors training in soft skills, by using successful examples. These efforts should be registered in the proposals showing the crucial role of MAA.	Medium
		4.2.4	Use funding schemes to support the development of networks and provide advice on network development and its role for innovation.	Long
4.3	Proposal development initiation and coordination remains mostly in the hands of universities and research organisations and in some cases some other large-scale organisations.	4.3.1	Implement stricter evaluation criteria for MAA. Proposals should be scored lower if there is insufficient involvement of practice partners, regardless of the quality of other areas.	Long
		4.3.2	Create a buddy network where experienced project partners mentor newcomers. Pair new coordinators with seasoned partners to provide advice and guidance.	Medium

3.4 Challenge Block #4: Developing proposals for MAA calls

Ch. No.	Final synthesis challenges		Final synthesis solutions	Solution Timeframe
		4.3.3	Support and encourage the involvement of EIP-AGRI OGs in MA Horizon proposals. OGs are valuable national activities for training and leading multi-actor networks, having already established multi-actor networks. The leading organization of the OG can be the actual partner in the project, with the OG itself being involved. Emphasize the inclusion of OGs in call texts, and further highlight their importance in informational events and brochures.	Short
4.4	The administrative burden for smaller organisations/partners to become beneficiaries in a project is challenging.	4.4.1	Strengthen support mechanisms to engage and support small partners in navigating administrative processes and securing financial resources.	Medium
4.5	It is challenging for newcomers to search for and join a consortium for the first time. While marketplaces and brokerage events aim to address this, they are often insufficient due to language barriers and the dominance of experienced organizations that do not rely on these events to build their consortia. Consequently, newcomers struggle to access pre-formed consortia.	4.5.1	Enhance and diversify networking opportunities, organize targeted marketplaces specifically designed for newcomers, ensuring they can engage with experienced organizations and key players in the network.	Short - Medium
		4.5.2	Newcomers need to invest time in joining stakeholder platforms or joining workshops to get a foot in the door of the big players, over a few years EU network involvement is an investment. This starts with training, getting to know the network better, going in person to brokerage events, contacting known partners and searching for organisations who have been or are part of a project, etc.	Short
		4.5.3	Increase the availability of cascade funding for non-tech projects.	Medium
4.6	It is challenging to reach and engage small partners (the agri-food system has 99% SMEs). Effective mechanisms, such as clusters, research centers, and regional associations, are required to streamline funding and research needs, though there is significant diversity in how these structures are organized across Member States.	4.6.1	Learn from the OGs and introduce similar solutions to other groups that also are expected to adopt the MA approach. Sectoral clusters and enterprise networks exist, but there is a lack of connection that networks the MAA. There is no need to reinvent the wheel but learn from models and clusters on the way they operate - the strategy of learning and focusing on improvement. A Service Point collecting and distributing information can support the MAA clusters community.	Long

3.4 Challenge Block #4: Developing proposals for MAA calls

Ch. No.	Final synthesis challenges		Final synthesis solutions	Solution Timeframe
		4.6.2	Use NCPs to help coordinators identify and connect with potential partners. Organize regular training sessions on partner identification, project topics, and the application process. Strengthen brokerage events by ensuring they are well-publicized and accessible to all relevant participants. See also 4.2.	Short
4.7	MAA call topics can address wicked situations, i.e. with general little agreement on objectives or issues, many interdependent factors and very difficult to solve. MAA is appropriate for addressing these wicked problems, but there are additional challenges to demonstrate and evaluate the contribution of consortium proposals and their methodologies.	4.7.1	Projects should be seen as contributors to ongoing transformation processes rather than complete or finalised solutions. This means managing projects in a way that builds people's skills to continue transformative efforts even after the project ends. This approach aligns with MAA's goal of connecting research with real-world dynamics, using tools like living labs, EIP-Agri groups and lighthouses	Short
4.8	Opening the consortium for other types of actors makes the proposal development process (and later on implementation) more time-consuming. This might bias the MAA that is then covered by a 'stakeholder engagement strategy' during implementation or alike, not in line with the true meaning of the MAA, creating issues during implementation.	4.8.1	Paying attention to the needs of each entity present in the group and help to move as close as possible to these goals. Raising awareness regarding these individual interests of partners. Ensure that everyone's expectations are in the project, then the project goes well. It's a balancing act that can be achieved if a space for improvisation is introduced in the project.	Short

3.5 Challenge Block #5: Implementing MAA projects in practice

Ch. No.	Final synthesis challenges		Final synthesis solutions	Solution Timeframe
5.1	Ensuring equitable participation of actors and stakeholders during the project requires addressing the compensation / benefits for those who are not direct beneficiaries.	5.1.1	Provide clearer guidance to coordinators on the different financial options available for reimbursing stakeholder and actor involvement efforts. Include detailed explanations of each option's pros and cons to help coordinators make informed decisions.	Short - Medium
		5.1.2	Cost/incentive for end-user involvement in proposal preparation: look for examples or good practices.	Short
		5.1.3	Compensation of end-users for participating in project activities: inform applicants during Info Days on existing rules on service contracts, travel cost for project meetings, prizes and vouchers	Short - Medium
		5.1.4	Base new calls on predefined R&I agendas that are drafted with and by stakeholders, ensuring the balance of different territorial needs. This approach allows MAA proposals to be seen by actors as effective tools for implementing these agendas and achieving the desired outputs, even if it requires more than one project cycle.	Long
		5.1.5	Strong communication of non-financial motivation, i.e positive image, networking, new connections	Short
		5.1.6	An EU Hub to support different types of organisations being part of MA Projects and help them with their participation, e.g. EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub	Long
5.2	Language and cultural barriers, and differences in regional capabilities can hinder participation. Some stakeholders may lack language skills for international collaboration.	5.2.1	Translate key events and key materials and include a basic glossary with translation of terms. Determine responsible body and means of funding to ensure these translations.	Long
5.3	The additional workload associated with MAA activities is significant, and these efforts are insufficiently recognized/rewarded in academic professional promotion/career improvement systems.	5.3.1	Offer a new dissemination fund allowing completed projects to apply for additional exploitation activities post-project. This scheme could be designed following the model of German Ag Agency's program to support further dissemination and impact of project results.	Long
		5.3.2	As education is not an EU policy, solutions to this have to develop at national level in Member States	Long
		5.3.3	Introduce a two-stage approach, where successful first-round ideas receive funding for further elaboration and allocate additional funds to support internal functioning and communication.	Long

3.5 Challenge Block #5: Implementing MAA projects in practice

Ch. No.	Final synthesis challenges		Final synthesis solutions	Solution Timeframe
5.4	There is a need to ensure that exploitation activities extend beyond the HEU project consortium network to achieve greater impact.	5.4.1	Offer more practical examples of how a MAA can be included in project design, detailing what works in the implementation and what doesn't.	Short
		5.4.2	The MAA DiverIMPACTS* project includes a policy brief on actionable knowledge development with recommendations on changes to proposal development and project governances and recommendations to research policy design that can be used to further the recommendations here.	Short
5.5	Engaging actors in MAA projects requires tailored communication for each group (e.g., policymakers, entrepreneurs, researchers, etc.). Aligning research outcomes with actors' needs, local and regional development targets, and social acceptance is challenging. Internal conflicts within multi-actor consortia can arise requiring multiple, time-consuming discussions.	5.5.1	See 5.1 Solutions	---
5.6	Allocating budget to support farmers participating in projects, beyond just research activities, is challenging. Ensuring the sustainability of these actions after the project ends is also crucial.	5.6.1	See 5.1 Solutions	---
5.7	Involvement of 'real' practitioners/end-users as partners can be challenging, especially as projects are often led by the academic sector. Need for early and meaningful engagement and appropriate financial reward for all partners.	5.7.1	Use and engage existing local agricultural networks, such as demonstration platforms, observatories, open farms, and living labs, early in the project to include relevant practitioners and end-users. Organize open days and demonstration activities to foster collaboration. Start dissemination and communication activities at the project's outset to capture and integrate all relevant actors' feedback, involving social scientists to ensure effective integration. Clearly define the distinct roles and tasks of each actor type in the project proposal and execution plan.	Short
		5.7.2	Provide more information on the link between the EIP-AGRI OG, EU CAP Network and Cluster 6 to ensure that relevant actors have access to Cluster 6 opportunities.	Medium

3.5 Challenge Block #5: Implementing MAA projects in practice

Ch. No.	Final synthesis challenges		Final synthesis solutions	Solution Timeframe
		5.7.3	Create a database with the information of networks or relevant entities and make it accessible to project coordinators during the planning phase to help coordinators search for and identify different actors needed for their projects.	Long
		5.7.4	Develop hands-on guidance documents to help coordinators identify and support small partner organizations (<i>see PREMIERE Brokerages</i>)	Short
5.8	Budgeting for MAA activities is difficult due to uncertainty in the number of external experts required and the transfer of funds between categories, limiting project efficacy.	5.8.1	The number of external experts to be involved and the associated budget is not known. But the project can make a rough estimate. As long as the budget position is in place, shifting is possible and if not possible, then Amendments are an option. However, a substantial share of the budget needs to be reserved for actors - independent if they were involved as actors or come later as stakeholders.	Short
5.9	MAA projects lack the necessary flexibility. They should be managed as complex systems with adaptive management approaches. Consortia needs flexibility to include and exclude partners as needed, and projects should allocate budgets for unforeseen needs.	5.9.1	Allow consortia more flexibility in including and excluding partners as project needs evolve. Allocate part of the budget as 'seed money' to address needs as they arise during the project. The longer a project the more relevance for flexibility.	Long
5.10	There is often a lack of leadership skills among the coordinators and consortium members to engage different actors.	5.10.1	Start building capacity in MAA projects by enhancing the common understanding of MAA. Address the identified impediments at various levels: individual, local team, project team, and the overarching innovation system to be aware or try to overcome them.	Medium
		5.10.2	Provide training courses for coordinators on how to handle the challenges of MAA and engage different actors.	Medium
		5.10.3	Create and distribute tools to help coordinators address key questions about actor collaboration and conflict resolution. These tools may already exist in projects such as LIAISON* or EUREKA* and should be better disseminated.	Short
5.11	Effectively communicating research and integrating practitioners' practical knowledge during the project is essential but challenging.	5.11.1	Consortia should include at least one social science partner to enhance communication and collaboration among various actors.	Short
5.12	There is a need to ensure a better impact of the project by supporting actions beyond the project lifetime or allowing for the continuation of projects.	5.12.1	European Network of Living Labs - Can this association have any role in identifying solutions to these challenges?	Short

3.5 Challenge Block #5: Implementing MAA projects in practice

Ch. No.	Final synthesis challenges		Final synthesis solutions	Solution Timeframe
5.13	Many research activities require more time than the project duration to produce peer-reviewed and robust results useful to practitioners. This can lead to disappointment among practitioners and researchers being uneasy about sharing preliminary results. Clear identification of activities expected to produce ready-for-practice results is needed.			---
5.14	The AKIS system that may underpin the multi-actor approach is not known or not widely shared beyond the sphere of agricultural technical institutes and advisers who have already taken part in European projects.			---
5.15	Solutions are needed to tackle the problem of overwhelming stakeholders with requests to participate in multiple proposals that exceed their capacity to manage these demands. This is the question of 'stakeholder fatigue'			---

4 RECOMMENDATIONS ON THE MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH DEFINITION

Participants' input related to improving the definition of the MAA and other work programme content suggestions were extracted and compiled. These suggestions emerged throughout the focus group process, and although similar suggestions are gathered together, they are listed exactly as proposed, meaning that some may overlap or repeat the same idea.

Table 2 presents the specific recommendations for refining the definition of the MAA.

Table 2: Suggested improvements to the MAA definition

Number	Suggested improvements to the MAA definition.
1 Distinction between partners and stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include a clear distinction about project partners/actors and external stakeholders. • The MAA requirements should clearly distinguish between consortium members and external stakeholders. Creating two separate lists for these requirements would help in compliance checking. • The roles and perceptions of consortium members (actors) and non-consortium members (stakeholders) are often unclear. This distinction needs to be more clearly defined in the MAA description. • Applicants often struggle with understanding the distinction between stakeholders and actors. This difference is not clearly described in the official MAA definition in the WP. Including this distinction in the WP could help.
2 End-user involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement for specific end-user involvement to be defined in the topic text is not straightforward as it is not only about specific end-user inclusion in consortium but also his/her role in the project activities. • Requirement # 2 refers both to excellence and consortium composition: make a separate requirement related to end-user representation in consortium composition.
3 Clarification of added value requirement	The requirement to demonstrate a project's added value should be reconsidered or clarified to avoid redundancy, as this is relevant for all projects, not just MAA.

Number	Suggested improvements to the MAA definition.
<p>4 Reference to co-design and co-creation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MAA is a form of co-design and co-creation, but this is not clearly referenced. Presenting MAA as a completely new concept can be misleading for participants. <i>(Note by PREMIERE, the definition starts with 'The multi-actor approach described here - a form of responsible R&I, aims to make the R&I process and its outcomes more reliable, demand-driven, shared and relevant to society.' We understand it acknowledges this wider concept, still co-design / co-creation could be added here)</i> The MAA definition mentions the MAA in a wider RRI context, perhaps a solution may be the addition of co-creation there and emphasis when communicating.
<p>5 Length and visibility of MAA definition</p>	<p>The MAA definition in the WP is a bit long. It would be beneficial to flag MAA topics in the cross-cutting priority filters of the F&T portal and update references from EIP-Agri to EU CAP Network.</p>
<p>6 Inclusion of cross-fertilization elements</p>	<p>Adding “experiences” to the list of cross-fertilization elements could enhance clarity.</p>
<p>7 Number of Practice Abstracts</p>	<p>The number of Practice Abstracts to be developed in a single project is unclear, adding to the complexity. Explicit reference to Practice Abstracts in the topic text (where required) would ensure applicants take this into account already when designing the proposal. Also, the indication of an “appropriate number” could be further specified and linked to objective elements (e.g. size of the project)</p>
<p>8 Duplication in evaluation criteria</p>	<p>MAA concept is redundant and is reflected in different main evaluation criteria. Simplification and harmonization should be sought. (For ex: do we really need to include in the definition: “It must demonstrate the project's added value: how it will complement existing research”) and best practices.</p>
<p>9 Number of requirements</p>	<p>The 7 requirements are too many, they are not concrete enough</p>
<p>10 Realistic objectives for TRL</p>	<p>MAA does not always result in ready to use (TRL up to 8) solutions at the end of the projects, while the definition and requirements clearly indicate that this should be the primary objective.</p>

Finally, table 3 includes additional recommendations for the Cluster 6 Work Programme content related to the MAA.

Table 3: Suggested improvements to Work Programme content

Number	Other Work Programme content suggestions
1	The requirement for practice abstracts and EU-wide communication in the EIP-AGRI format is often not reflected at the topic level. This necessitates revisions during the GAP phase. Explicit references to practice abstracts and specifying an appropriate number based on project size would ensure better compliance from the start.
2	Since PREMIERE offers and has prepared more detailed information, could the project at least be mentioned in the WP / a reference with a link in the footnote and even in the application template? In the latter, more precise instructions on how this should be incorporated/addressed would be desirable.
3	MAA should NOT be a technical obligation but an eligibility criterion.
4	Better connect the definition (WP Introduction) with the actual MAA topic texts. It is suggested to make this/these definition(s) of MAA much more prominent in the work programme. This could be as simple as an asterisk as soon as the word appears, but it's absolutely necessary for the resource to be readily available as soon as you read the topics.
5	A reference to the work programme page where the definition can be found should appear on each call.
6	Topic text sometimes does not explicitly include MAA in the body of the topic text, leaving it only to the general 'Mandatory MAA' statement at the end of the topic.
7	MAA used in topics in many areas beyond agriculture, MAA features can be a burden & MAA mainstreaming can be counterproductive: target MAA for F2F topics or when there is a need for actors to be part of the project (e.g. to cover entire value chain)

5 REFERENCES

5.1 Documents generated during the Focus Group process

1. **Background paper** – a document that provides a general framework to open the debate and set the base for the initial discussion.
2. **Synthesis Table of Challenges** – a synthesized summary of all identified challenges from individual contributions in the 5 key actor groups from the first phase of discussions.
3. **Synthesis Table of Challenges and Solutions** – a summary of all identified challenges, provided solutions, and recommendations, divided into challenge clusters.

5.2 Other documents of relevance

1. **Definition of the Multi-actor Approach** – European Commission. (2023-2025). Horizon Europe [Work Programme. 9. Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment](#). European Commission Decision C(2024) 2371 of 17 April 2024. Accessed 29.04.2024.
2. **Horizon Europe On-line Manual**. Funding & Tenders Portal. Visited 19.4.2024.
3. **ESR Policy Brief** – Pietx, J. and M.Redman. 2023. Discussion paper: Expression of the Multi-Actor Approach in Evaluation Summary Reports (ESR) in Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe proposals: analysis, trends, and applications. Horizon PREMIERE. <https://zenodo.org/records/8377184>
4. **PREMIERE project Padlet board**. Visited 2.5.2024.
5. **Policy Brief on Producing Actionable Knowledge** – Walter Rossing, Luca Colombo, Barbara Koole, Antoine Messéan.2022. Producing Actionable Knowledge for Crop Diversification. Horizon DiverIMPACTS. <https://zenodo.org/record/6353589>
6. **Care4Bio annotated templates (RIA, IA & CSA)** - annotated proposal templates for both first stage and full proposals for Research and Innovation Actions (RIA) / Innovation Actions (IA) and Coordination and Support Actions (CSA).
7. **LIAISON** – Interactive Innovation Toolbox
8. **EUREKA** – Public network for international cooperation in R&D and innovation.

6 ANNEXES

ANNEX 1: Overview of Number of Participants by Key Actor Groups

PREMIERE Facilitating team	Kaie Laaneväli-Vinokurov (METK)
	Jordi Pietx (HCC)
	Mark Redman (HCC)
	Susanne v. Münchhausen (HNEE)
	Evelien Cronin (ILVO)
	Mikelis Grivins (BSC)
	Laura Quijano (CIHEAM)
	Maarja Pikkmetts (KKLM)
	Valentina Carta (CREA)
Total of 51 participants contributed to the focus group	

Actor group	No of participants	% from all the participants
Policy officers	13	25%
Project officers	8	16%
NCPs	7	14%
External experts	5	10%
Project coordinators and other informed/interested stakeholders/experts	18	35%

ANNEX 2: CHALLENGES PROPOSED THAT ARE EXCLUDED FROM THIS FINAL REPORT

The following challenges were identified during the focus group process but are not included in the final compilation in section 3 of this report. In brackets and *italics*, the reason for exclusion is indicated.

- CL 1 MAA material on agriculture only could be misleading: in Horizon Europe, MAA is applied to many areas beyond agriculture, so when presenting best practices or successful projects, it would be good to cover the variety of areas under CL6. There is a large variety of end-users, not only farmers and foresters, as presented in the definition, so it is important to reflect this variety when producing communication material on MAA. *(This challenge and a potential solution are already covered by 1.2)*
- CL2 Evaluators face difficulties due to language barriers, conceptual inconsistencies, and unclear application of MAA across similar topics. *(discarded by the participants to the final focus group in considering that Language is not a challenge during the evaluation process nor on the written proposals).*
- CL3 Enabling environment means that there is sufficient information available (clear definition, guidelines, examples of good practices etc.) that helps applicants to understand the philosophy of MAA. MAA idea has been in the framework program for 10 years, but it is still differently understood. If MAA is considered important by the funding authority, then it should give it more emphasis in the evaluation phase, so that evaluators are able to recognise a convincing MAA. *(This has been considered a definition and not a challenge)*
- CL4 There is a significant gap between the interests and motives of academic and non-academic partners, making it difficult and more challenging to develop an excellent MAA. *(merged into a single 4.2)*
- CL4 Engaging actors working across the agri-food value chain, such as cooperatives, wholesale, food industry, retail, and service, is challenging~While existing platforms are helpful, better implementation structures similar to EIP-AGRI are needed to fully embrace the food industry and food retail. *(merged into a single 4.2).*
- CL4. Coordinators need assistance in finding appropriate partners, especially SMEs, farmers and other producers, civil society organisations and policymakers, who may not be visible online or active in academic networks. *(merged into a single 4.2)*

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